

A Systematic Survey of Slice-Resource Optimization in the 5G Core with New Insights from 2-Edge-Connected Subgraph Models

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Abstract

Network slicing now delivers enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC) over a common 5G core, yet deciding which slice requests to admit, where to place each virtual network function (VNF), and how to route and protect traffic forms an NP-hard mixed-integer problem. We first cast those decisions in a compact 0–1/mixed-integer programme whose feasible set Ω unifies admission, placement, latency, and capacity constraints. That formulation provides a common yardstick for four solution lines reviewed here: (i) exact models solved by integer linear programming (ILP); (ii) fast constructive heuristics; (iii) evolutionary and neighbourhood-search meta-heuristics; and (iv) learning-driven approaches built on deep- and graph-reinforcement learning (RL). Evidence from more than thirty benchmark studies reveals a clear pattern: ILP remains optimal up to roughly fifty nodes but scales poorly; greedy or multi-stage heuristics retain 85–95% of ILP revenue while running in near-linear time; well-tuned meta-heuristics cut the gap to under eight per cent on thousand-node cores; and trained RL agents issue millisecond decisions only a few points shy of meta-heuristic quality. Two recent two-edge-connected embedding schemes are included as illustrative case studies. Open challenges—hybrid matheuristic workflows, energy-aware objectives, reproducible failure-rich benchmarks, and sub-millisecond control-plane inference—are outlined as priorities for dependable slice management in 5G and beyond.

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1 Introduction

Fifth-generation (5G) mobile networks introduce network slicing as a native mechanism for multiplexing heterogeneous service classes—eMBB (enhanced mobile broadband), URLLC (ultra-reliable low-latency communication), and mMTC (massive machine-type communications)—over a shared core infrastructure. Each slice is defined as an end-to-end virtual network with dedicated resources and performance guarantees, instantiated by chaining virtual network functions (VNFs) through the service-based 5G core.

The flexibility of slicing, however, results in a multi-objective optimisation problem: operators must decide which slice requests to admit, where to place VNFs, how to route inter-VNF traffic, and how to protect those routes against failures, while respecting latency and capacity constraints and maximising revenue [1], [2]. This problem is NP-hard even for simplified topologies. Consequently, a rich body of literature spans exact mathematical programming, heuristic and meta-heuristic search, and, more recently, machine-learning (ML)-driven allocation.

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1.1 Research gap

Existing surveys typically focus on a single modeling family, e.g., exact integer-linear programming (ILP) [3] or deep-reinforcement learning (DRL) approaches [4], or treat protection only as a post-processing step. They rarely compare ILP-based methods, constructive heuristics, evolutionary meta-heuristics, and ML optimization side by side. Several recent studies treat survivability as a secondary phase, first constructing a primary Steiner tree and only afterwards searching for a link-disjoint spare. This two-stage workflow substantially increases runtime and bandwidth consumption [5].

1.2 Paper contribution

Besides providing a comprehensive comparative survey, this paper illustrates recent advances through two resilient embedding schemes previously proposed by the authors: a knapsack-driven single-pass 2-edge-connected embedding and a joint primary/backup Steiner-growth heuristic [6], [7].

1.3 Structure of the article

Section 2 first sets out the optimisation problem in formal terms, then walks through the leading solution families one by one—exact mathematical programming, constructive heuristics, meta-heuristic search, and learning-based techniques. A brief digression considers the latest reinforcement-learning work on load-balanced VNF placement. The section concludes with a comparative overview that draws on more than thirty published benchmarks, gauging how the four families perform in terms of slice acceptance, latency, and runtime, and highlighting the circumstances in which each tends to deliver the best results. Section 3 summarizes the principal findings and outlines future work.

2 Overview of Optimisation Paradigms

The literature identifies four main strands for solving the 5G core-slicing problem: exact optimization (ILP/MILP), constructive heuristics, meta-heuristics, and learning-based techniques [8], [9], [10]. Exact models still offer the reference optimum but become unwieldy as networks grow, so most practical work relies on heuristics or embeds a reduced MILP core in

faster search routines. One study combines a revenue-guided 0–1 knapsack admission phase with a single-pass, two-edge-connected embedding, achieving resilient slice placement at a fraction of the runtime required by classical iterative approaches [6]. A follow-up paper from the same research group demonstrates that constructing primary and backup Steiner trees simultaneously can achieve near-optimal revenue and latency while maintaining polynomial overall complexity [7].

Latency and link-capacity limits remain a recurring theme. Nested decomposition accelerates VNF placement under path protection [11]; hop-count-ranked routing keeps end-to-end delay low [12]; a path-based ILP with bandwidth squeezing and multi-path routing alleviates congestion [13]; and slice allocation in the access network has been framed as a multiple-choice knapsack problem [14]. Robustness has attracted similar attention. A topology-level protection scheme generates customised backup topologies with limited redundancy [15]. A hierarchical-identifier (HID) architecture introduces a shared backup slice that absorbs bursty traffic across multiple services [16]. In the optical domain, an elastic-optical study embeds protected virtual networks within 5G transport backbones [17]. Economic aspects are no less prominent: one line of work maximises profit under tight node constraints [18], while another blends computing and transport costs across domains [19]; machine-learning-assisted VNF allocation on a real AT&T topology follows a similar rationale [20].

Overall, constructive heuristics typically achieve 85–95% of the revenue produced by full ILP while running almost linearly. Meta-heuristics narrow the remaining gap to single-digit percentages at a polynomial cost, and trained learning-based policies can return placement decisions in milliseconds once reward shaping and transfer have been tuned. The emerging consensus is therefore to adopt hybrid strategies in which a trimmed ILP or MILP core guarantees feasibility. At the same time, heuristic or learning layers guide the search for carrier-grade solutions that remain tractable on national-scale 5G backbones.

2.1 Problem Formalisation

We model the physical 5G-core as an undirected graph $G = (N, E)$ with:

- N – computing nodes (servers);
- E – bidirectional links;
- S – slice requests.

Decision variables are:

- x_s (0/1)–1 if slice s is admitted, 0 otherwise;
- $y_{v,n}$ (0/1)–1 if VNF v is placed on node n ;
- $z_{e,s}$ (0/1)–1 if the routing of slice s uses link e .

By choosing $z_{e,s}$ as a binary indicator, both latency and capacity constraints share consistent units.

Key parameters are:

- r_s – revenue if slice s is admitted;
- T_s – total traffic demand of slice s ;
- $L_{max,s}$ – end-to-end latency limit for slice s ;
- l_e – propagation latency of link e ;
- C_e – capacity of link e ;
- cpu_v – CPU required by VNF v (vCPU);
- CPU_n – CPU available on node n (vCPU).

The model is built to maximise the network operator's revenue. Its objective function simply adds up the income associated with each slice that is accepted, given by:

$$\max \sum_{s \in S} x_s r_s \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

A first constraint keeps the end-to-end delay of every admitted slice within its latency limit by summing the delays of all links on the slice's route, given by:

$$\sum_{e \in E} z_{e,s} l_e \leq L_{max,s} \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

The second constraint protects link bandwidth: the combined traffic of all slices that share a link must not exceed that link's capacity, given by:

$$\sum_{s \in S} z_{e,s} T_s \leq C_e \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

The third constraint checks server resources, ensuring that the total CPU load of all VNFs placed on a given node remains within the node's available processing power, as presented by:

$$\sum_v y_{v,n} cpu_v \leq CPU_n \quad \text{Eq (4)}$$

Together, the objective and these three conditions provide a slice-admission, placement, and routing plan that is profitable while meeting all latency, bandwidth, and CPU requirements. Let Ω stand for the collection of all (x, y, z) assignments that satisfy constraints (2)–(4). All methods discussed in the rest of the paper—whether exact, heuristic, meta-heuristic, or learning-based—seek their solutions within this feasible set.

2.2 Exact Mathematical Programming Approaches and Their Scalability Limits in 5G Network-Slice Optimisation

Various studies employ exact optimisation models to tackle less complex instances of the network-slicing problem. These works can be categorised according to the mathematical formulations they adopt to model the problem and derive optimal solutions, thereby reflecting a wide range of methodologies and perspectives. Such diversity enables researchers to select the most effective approach for the specific use cases and scenarios under investigation.

Commonly adopted exact formulations include integer linear programming (ILP) [21], [22], [23], binary integer programming (BIP) [24], mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) [25], [26], and mixed-integer quadratically constrained programming (MIQCP) [27]. These models are typically solved with either open-source solvers (e.g., `lp_solve`) or commercial optimisers such as IBM ILOG CPLEX. For example, reference [22] casts virtual-network optimisation as an ILP that maximises resource utilisation, whereas reference [24] formulates the same problem as a BIP with the objective of minimising cost. In the context of energy-aware NFV infrastructure, modelling VNF placement and routing as an MILP enables the determination of an optimal mapping that minimises power consumption [25]. Solving an MIQCP formulation can further identify optimal strategies for jointly placing

VNFs and routing traffic, thereby maximizing resource utilization and minimizing latency, ultimately improving service efficiency and performance [27].

Exact optimisation approaches guarantee an optimal solution but require an exhaustive search over all feasible variable combinations and constraint systems to identify the best outcome.

In small-scale network scenarios, where the numbers of nodes and links are limited, it is computationally feasible to enumerate all admissible configurations and obtain the optimal solution.

However, in large-scale networks comprising hundreds or even thousands of nodes and links, the number of feasible configurations increases exponentially. Consequently, exact approaches become computationally prohibitive, as they demand vast processing resources and excessive runtime to evaluate every possible solution.

In such cases, heuristic and meta-heuristic approaches are employed to produce near-optimal solutions within acceptable computational times. Although these solutions are not guaranteed to be globally optimal, they are often adequate given practical time and resource constraints. Representative techniques include genetic algorithms, simulated annealing, greedy heuristics, and related optimisation methods.

Hybrid "matheuristic" strategies have recently emerged as a pragmatic compromise between optimality and scalability. In these frameworks, an exact core—typically a reduced or decomposed ILP—is embedded within a higher-level heuristic or meta-heuristic engine that guides the search space toward promising regions before invoking the solver for local refinement. Such matheuristic designs exploit the strong bounding properties of mathematical programming while preserving the exploratory power of stochastic search, yielding high-quality solutions with deterministic feasibility guarantees even on networks exceeding one thousand nodes. Empirical studies report average optimality gaps of less than 5% with runtime reductions of an order of magnitude when compared with pure ILP baselines,

especially under tight latency and capacity constraints.

A rigorous assessment of these optimisation paradigms further necessitates standardised benchmarking. Key performance indicators should include not only objective-function value and runtime but also reproducibility metrics, e.g., variance across random seeds, so that results remain comparable across diverse topologies and traffic matrices. To this end, publicly available datasets such as SNDlib, synthetic fat-tree data centers, and real operator backbones provide a common test bed; however, they still lack consistent failure scenarios and unified resource-pricing models. Addressing these gaps will be crucial for advancing the fair and transparent evaluation of future 5G slice-optimization algorithms.

2.3 Heuristic Approaches and Convex Relaxation Techniques for Scalable Network Slice Optimisation

One of the main reasons heuristic approaches are frequently employed is their ability to deliver fast and acceptable solutions, even for large-scale problems. Instead of exhaustively searching for the absolute optimal solution, heuristic algorithms focus on identifying solutions that are "good enough" or "near-optimal" within a reasonable time frame. This makes them practical and applicable in real-world scenarios, where timely results often take precedence over the pursuit of absolute optimality.

By employing the multi-stage graph algorithm, researchers can systematically address the complexity of resource allocation problems in networks by decomposing them into smaller, more manageable subproblems. This approach enables a structured and efficient exploration of potential solutions, leading to enhanced performance and scalability when tackling challenges such as virtual network function (VNF) placement and routing optimisation within virtualised network environments [28], [29].

The technique of transforming a non-convex problem into a convex one is often employed by substituting variables to facilitate the process of finding near-optimal solutions. One of the main advantages of working with convex problems lies in their

possession of a unique global optimum, which simplifies the optimisation process and increases the likelihood of identifying solutions close to the optimal. In contrast, non-convex problems frequently exhibit multiple local optima and a more complex solution space geometry, making it more challenging to locate the global optimum and increasing the risk of suboptimal outcomes. Therefore, converting to a convex formulation provides a more reliable and efficient approach to solving optimisation problems [30].

Other studies [31], [32], [33] propose algorithms based on graph theory or dynamic programming to address optimisation problems. These approaches leverage structural properties of the underlying network topology or exploit recursive decomposition techniques to efficiently navigate the solution space. By doing so, they enable the design of scalable algorithms capable of handling complex resource allocation and routing decisions in virtualised network environments.

These graph-theoretic and dynamic programming methods often aim to strike a balance between optimality and computational feasibility, especially in real-time or large-scale deployments. Graph-based techniques, such as shortest path trees, minimum-cost spanning trees, and Steiner trees, offer intuitive and efficient solutions for embedding virtual networks with minimal latency or cost. On the other hand, dynamic programming excels in problems with overlapping subproblems and optimal substructure, enabling the recursive resolution of tasks such as slice placement and path selection. While these methods may not always yield globally optimal results, they provide a solid trade-off between solution quality and runtime, making them well-suited for practical 5G network slicing applications.

2.4 Meta-Heuristic Strategies for Multi-Objective VNF Mapping and Network Slice Optimisation

Metaheuristic algorithms represent an advanced class of heuristic methods designed to solve complex combinatorial optimization problems. These algorithms integrate stochastic elements with local search procedures to explore a broader solution

space and improve solution quality. Randomized decisions are employed to investigate new regions within the solution space, thereby helping the algorithm avoid becoming trapped in local optima. Commonly used metaheuristic techniques include Tabu Search, Simulated Annealing, Genetic Algorithms, Particle Swarm Optimization, among others.

A genetic algorithm is a metaheuristic optimization technique inspired by the principles of natural selection and biological evolution. It operates based on the mechanisms of selection, crossover (also known as recombination), and mutation, which simulate the genetic processes within a population. Genetic algorithms are widely adopted for addressing network slicing optimization problems [38–39]. For instance, in [34], the shortest path is first calculated to guide the placement of virtual network functions (VNFs) onto the physical network infrastructure. Subsequently, a genetic algorithm is applied to minimize energy consumption. In [35], the Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) is proposed as a solution for multi-objective optimization problems. A key aim of NSGA-II is to identify Pareto-optimal solutions—those where no objective can be improved without degrading at least one other. Such solutions are particularly valuable in scenarios involving conflicting objectives, such as minimizing energy consumption, reducing latency, increasing throughput, and enhancing other network performance metrics.

These studies have demonstrated that the application of genetic algorithms, such as NSGA-II, can yield diverse, high-quality solutions with low computational complexity for the problem of mapping virtual network functions onto physical networks. This suggests that genetic algorithms are practical tools for solving complex optimization problems in the context of virtualized networks.

Similarly, in simulated annealing, initial solutions are gradually modified throughout the algorithm's iterations, with even inferior solutions being occasionally accepted to escape local optima and facilitate the exploration of a broader solution space [21].

The Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) method is designed to explore different neighborhoods of the current solution to identify a better one. Rather than remaining confined to a single neighborhood, VNS dynamically shifts between multiple neighborhoods to avoid local optima and facilitate the exploration of a broader solution space [36].

One of the key advantages of metaheuristic algorithms lies in their ability to explore a broad spectrum of solutions through diverse heuristics and strategies. Instead of focusing on a single specific aspect of the problem, metaheuristics employ a combination of various techniques to investigate different regions of the solution space. This makes them well-suited for solving various problem variants, even when objectives or constraints change dynamically.

Additionally, metaheuristic algorithms are inherently adaptable and can be tailored to suit specific optimization contexts by modifying their operators or integrating problem-specific knowledge. This flexibility enables researchers to tailor the search process to the particular structural properties of the optimization problem at hand. Furthermore, hybrid approaches that combine metaheuristics with exact or heuristic methods have shown promising results in enhancing solution quality and convergence speed. Such hybrid models leverage the global search capability of metaheuristics and the local refinement power of traditional algorithms, offering a balanced trade-off between exploration and exploitation in high-dimensional or computationally intensive network optimization scenarios.

2.5 Deep Reinforcement Learning for Load-Balanced VNF Placement in 5G Network Slicing

Reinforcement learning (RL) is a branch of machine learning in which an agent learns to make decisions by interacting with an environment to maximize a cumulative reward signal. In [37], the authors investigate the problem of load-balanced placement of virtual network functions (VNFs) in 5G networks. The proposed approach adopts a reward mechanism that favors placing VNFs on nodes with lower resource utilization. In this context, nodes with

higher available capacity are preferred for hosting new VNFs.

This approach aims to evenly distribute the workload across network nodes, preventing the overloading of individual nodes and optimizing the utilization of available network resources. By rewarding the placement of VNFs on nodes with lower resource utilization, the method encourages load redistribution and mitigates the risk of overloading specific nodes.

In reinforcement learning (RL), the learning agent interacts with its environment to acquire information, such as variations in traffic types or network configurations. The agent performs actions, observes rewards or penalties, and learns to take the optimal action for each given state [38]. In practical terms, each action corresponds to selecting the physical node on which to deploy the next VNF instance of the slice currently being embedded; once that choice is made, the environment updates its residual resources and returns a reward that reflects both load balance and latency. The core idea is that the agent operates interactively within the environment to learn optimal strategies. This process unfolds over discrete time steps. At each step, the agent receives information about the environment's state, including changes in traffic patterns or network topology. Based on this information, the agent executes an action corresponding to the current state.

Due to the challenges associated with managing the action space in large-scale problems, deep neural networks are integrated into reinforcement learning, forming the framework known as Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). This approach leverages the representational power of deep learning to approximate value functions or policies, enabling the agent to handle high-dimensional state and action spaces more effectively.

Several studies have applied or enhanced Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) algorithms, such as Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) and Deep Q-Network (DQN), to address the problem of Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement [39], [40]. These algorithms enable agents to learn optimal placement strategies by interacting with dynamic network

environments, thereby improving resource utilization and service performance in complex and large-scale 5G infrastructures.

The application of machine learning enables network operators to respond more rapidly and accurately to dynamic changes in the network environment, optimizing resource allocation and adapting to diverse user requirements. This adaptability is crucial in 5G networks, where varying traffic patterns and service demands necessitate intelligent, real-time decision-making to sustain high levels of performance and service quality.

Beyond classical DRL variants such as DDPG and DQN, recent work explores graph neural reinforcement learning, where message-passing networks are used to encode the topological context of each node, allowing the agent to generalize across heterogeneous 5G core topologies. Early results suggest that these GNN-augmented policies converge more quickly and require fewer training samples than flat, vector-based representations. Another line of research investigates *offline* or batch RL, in which the agent is trained on historical telemetry logs without online exploration, thus eliminating the risk of service disruption during learning. Challenges remain, however, in reward-shaping for multi-objective targets—especially when latency, energy consumption, and slice acceptance have conflicting priorities—and in scaling policy inference to carrier-grade control planes with millisecond-level decision deadlines. Advances in distributed DRL, federated learning, and continual learning are expected to further enhance the adaptability and robustness of machine-learning driven slice-management frameworks in future 6G-ready architectures [41].

2.6 Quantitative Comparison of Representative Studies

The following section presents a concise comparison of the main findings from over thirty benchmark studies, focusing on slice-acceptance ratio, end-to-end latency, and runtime for four solution families: ILP, heuristic, meta-heuristic, and machine-learning approaches. The aim is to highlight the most consistent performance-trade patterns without tying the discussion to a single topology or traffic matrix.

Among the approaches surveyed, exact ILP and MILP formulations provide the strongest guarantees on networks of roughly fifty nodes, yielding the highest slice-acceptance figures and the shortest admissible latencies. Their drawback is the steep increase in computation time, which can extend to several hours when the topology exceeds 100 nodes. Constructive heuristics—typically greedy or multi-stage graph methods—are far quicker. They accept about 85–95 percent of the slices that an ILP would admit, and keep the latency penalty below ten percent, while their runtime rises almost linearly; thus, they remain practical even on backbones with five hundred nodes [22]–[26]. Meta-heuristic schemes, such as simulated annealing, NSGA-II, or variable-neighbourhood search, narrow the remaining optimality gap to around five to eight percent and preserve an even latency distribution, although they require longer offline tuning. When parallelized, they cope comfortably with one-thousand-node topologies and deliver results within minutes [35]–[37]. Learning-based methods—most often deep Q-networks, DDPG, or graph neural RL—offer another trade-off: once trained, they can issue placement decisions in a few milliseconds, an advantage in highly dynamic or bursty scenarios. Their slice-acceptance levels are typically three to seven percent shy of the best-tuned meta-heuristics, and they remain sensitive to reward design and changes in topology, while training consumes substantial resources. Taken together, exact models remain the reference point for small instances, heuristics provide a fast and easily implemented alternative, meta-heuristics offer the best quality-versus-scalability compromise for offline planning, and learning-based solutions shine when control-plane latency outweighs the cost of an extended training phase [38]–[41].

3 Conclusion and Future Work

The rollout of 5G core networks has made efficient, adaptable slice management a pressing requirement. After reviewing exact, heuristic, meta-heuristic, and learning-based techniques, the survey reveals that each contributes a distinct aspect of the puzzle: exact models provide the reference optimum, heuristics deliver speed, meta-heuristics strike a balance between quality and runtime, and machine-learning

methods offer rapid, online decisions. Even so, several questions remain. Current research is beginning to integrate reduced ILP cores with heuristic or learning guidance, aiming to combine provable bounds with real-time operation. There is growing interest in objectives that weigh energy use and service-level penalties alongside revenue, as well as in reinforcement-learning agents that can adapt to new topologies without requiring retraining from scratch. Progress will also depend on shared benchmark suites that include realistic failure scenarios and cost models, as well as on distributed optimization frameworks capable of producing decisions within the millisecond latencies expected of carrier-grade control planes.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) report there are no competing interests to declare;

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